

D2.2 Symposium proceedings

Symposium on Directed evolution of proteins in Tatranska Lomnica, Slovakia

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (CasProt)**
No. 952333

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The [Symposium on Directed evolution of proteins](#) took part in Tatranská Lomnica in Gran Hotel Praha from April 28th to May 1st 2023. The intention of the Symposium was to get together experts on protein evolution and on protein design in general and protein characterization by state-of-the-art techniques such as a single molecule spectroscopy. The experts were invited from the partners laboratories of University of Zurich (UZH) (4 persons) and Technical University in Munich (TUM) (1 person) within the project CasProt as well as 2 principal investigators from laboratories collaborating on different projects with the laboratories at Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences (CIB), i.e. Loschmidt laboratories at Masaryk University in Brno, Czech republic and Neuroimmunology Institute of Slovak Academy of Sciences in Bratislava, Slovakia. Of 25 Symposium participants, 6 were the principal investigators of the group at CIB and 10 early stage researchers on different stage (PhD student, postdocs, young researcher) of their research careers. Lectures on the Symposium consisted from 9 lectures of principal investigators and 4 lectures of early stage researchers.

The program and the location of the Symposium offered numerous possibilities for discussions of young researchers with the principal investigators as well as for establishing new connections and networking among principal investigators.

Overall, the Symposium on Directed evolution of proteins was a successful event. The participants could take part in lectures presenting current topics in protein design and protein evolution. Moreover, this event led not only to an establishing of new and strengthening of already existing collaborations but also provided numerous opportunities to discuss scientific projects between young researchers and experiences principal investigators.

Web page: <https://www.upjs.sk/pracoviska/tip/en/sp/casprot/events/symposia/symposium-on-directed-evolution-of-proteins/>

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1. SYMPOSIUM PROGRAM

Symposium on directed evolution of proteins

Grand Hotel Praha, Tatranská Lomnica

April 28th, 2023 – Friday

- 16:00** Welcome and opening remarks - Erik Sedlák
- 16:05-16:30 Pavol Miškovský: **History and future of bioscience in Košice**
- 16:40-16:50 Erik Sedlák: **CasProt – current status**
- 17:00-17:45 Andreas Plückthun: **The design of evolution and the evolution of design**
- 18:00** Dinner
- 19:15** Welcome drink

April 29th, 2023 – Saturday

- 8:00** Breakfast
- 9:30-10:15 Matthias Rief: **Single molecule force spectroscopy for protein folding and cell adhesion**
- 10:25-11:10 Jozef Hanes: **Directed evolution of antibodies for detection of low abundant biomarkers in body fluids**
- 11:20-12:00 Zbyněk Prokop: **Transforming protein engineering: unleashing the power of kinetics, microfluidics and machine learning**
- 12:15** Lunch
- 15:00-15:30 Martin Humeník: **Directed self-assembly of spider silk protein on surfaces**
- 15:40-16:10 Gabriel Žoldák: **Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70**
- 16:20-16:50 Mária Tomková: **Directed evolution of staphylokinase by ribosome display**
- 17:00-17:30 Erik Sedlák: **Design of genetically encoded photosensitizers**
- 18:00** Dinner
- 19:15** Networking discussion

April 30th, 2023 – Sunday

- 8:00** Breakfast
- 10:40-11:50 Round table
- 12:15** Lunch
- Early researcher's presentations:**
- 15:30-15:50 Veronika Dzurillová: **Directed evolution of enzymes – the case of HLDs**
- 16:00-16:20 Veronika Džupponová: **Aggregation mechanism of myelomatic human light chain**
- 16:30-16:50 Michal Gala: **Computational evolutionary analysis of insertion and deletion events in bacterial Hsp70**
- 17:00-17:20 Veronika Hovanová: **Self-assembly of recombinant spider silk protein**
- 18:00-18:10 Closing remarks
- 18:00** Dinner

May 1st, 2023 – Monday

- 8:00 Breakfast

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 952333

2. PRESENTATIONS

2.1 History and future of Biosciences in Košice

Pavol Miškovský

Abstract: Development of biosciences in Košice has significantly accelerated upon obtaining the EU project Fostering Excellence in Multiscale Cell Imaging, acronym CELIM, in 2013. The origin of the present development, however, has been set up in the year 1998 by creating Department of Biophysics. Successful fulfilment of CELIM's goals led to formation of Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences (CIB) and Technology and Innovation Park at Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice (UPJŠ), what represented the first interdisciplinary "department" at UPJŠ. Integrative effort on the interuniversity level led to establishing of Cassovia New Industry Cluster (CNIC). The CNIC presently consists of 7 groups with expertise in nanotechnologies, biophotonics, targeted cancer therapy, tissue engineering, protein engineering, protein evolution, bioenergetics, development of new bionanomaterials from amyloid fibrils, analysis of aggregation and fibrillization processes and advanced cellular technology. The future of Biosciences in Košice significantly depends on predictable and continual financial support through grants on national and/or european level.

History and future of Biosciences in Košice (selected slides)

History and future of Biosciences in Košice (selected slides)

BIOSCIENMCES – INTEGRATION WITH THE GROUPS FROM OTHER UNIVERSITIES AND SAS

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| <p>1 prof. RNDr. Pavol Miškovsky, DrSc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NANOTECHNOLOGIES, • BIOPHOTONICS • TARGETED CANCER THERAPY • TISSUE ENGINEERING | <p>2 doc. RNDr. Erik Sedlák, DrSc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DEVELOPMENT OF NEW THROMBOLYTICS • DEVELOPMENT OF NEW ENZYMES • GENETICALLY CODED PHOTSENSITIZERS • NEW MOLECULAR PLATFORMS | <p>3 doc. Mgr. Daniel Jancura, PhD.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIOENERGETICS AND AGING • ARTIFICIAL PHOTOSYNTHESIS |
| <p>4 doc. RNDr. Zuzana Gažová, DrSc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IDENTIFICATION OF NEW MOLECULES AND NANOPARTICLES PREVENTING AMYLOID • IMPROVING THE STABILITY OF THERAPEUTICS • NEW BIONANOMATERIALS FROM AMYLOID FIBRILS | <p>5 doc. MVDr. Mangesh Ramesh Bhide, PhD.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CREATION OF NANOBODIES • C7C PEPTIDES AGAINST NEUROINVASIVE PATHOGENS | <p>6 doc. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, PhD.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEW MOLECULES PREVENTING THE FORMATION OF LIGHT CHAIN AGGREGATES • STABILIZING EXCIPIENTS |
| <p>7 ADVANCED CELLULAR TECHNOLOGY GROUP – IN COLLABORATION WITH TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY
NEW GROUP RECENTLY ESTABLISHED</p> | | |

CNIC

TECHNOLOGY DRIVEN, HUMAN ORIENTED

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CASSOVIA NEW INDUSTRY CLUSTER- PARTNERS

Cassovia New Industry Cluster is an association of legal entities (partners) from the public and private sectors

CNIC

TECHNOLOGY DRIVEN, HUMAN ORIENTED

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History and future of Biosciences in Košice (selected slides)

CNIC - TECHNOLOGY AREAS

CNIC's technological focus based on regional excellence & guaranteed by personalities from science, technology and industry with an international reputation

Technology areas	Future material and biomedical technologies				Future green technologies		Future quantum and information technologies
Technology and innovation centers	Center for interdisciplinary biosciences/CIB	Center for progressive materials/CPM	Center for biomedical engineering/CBE	Center for translation medicine/CTM	Center for green & digital technologies/CGDT	Center for hydrogen technologies/CHT	Center for quantum & information technologies/CQIT
Big data management	Supercomputer						
Social sciences	Technology vs. society – sociology, psychology, law, ethics "responsible system of society governance/regulation"						
Technology transfer	Start-up incubator 		Start-up accelerator 		Established societies already on the market (created in CNIC): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ SAFTRA photonics s.r.o. ➢ RVMagnetics s.r.o. ➢ Biomedical Engineering s.r.o. ➢ SAFTRA BioMAI s.r.o. 		
Business & marketing	scouting, IP protection and management, CNIC investment fund management, business relationship with high-tech companies, licensing policy, internal state aid rules <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Signed MoU and collaboration agreements with domestic as well as foreign companies 						

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CURRENT ACTIVITIES IN BIOSCIENCES

Project I: Strategic development of the infrastructure of the Košice University Campus (54 mil. € - Recovery and resilience plan for Slovakia)

Activity 1: School of interdisciplinary biosciences and biomedical engineering (between SAFARIK university, Technical university and University of veterinary medicine)

Activity 2: Reinforcement of the teams working in the field of Interdisciplinary biosciences and biomedical engineering (CIB, CBE, CTM, CQIT)

Activity 3: New laboratory space for Interdisciplinary biosciences and biomedical engineering

Project II: HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-01 (Teaming for Excellence) (15 mil. €)
CREATION OF A CENTER OF EXCELLENCE - INSTITUTE FOR INTERDISCIPLINARY BIOSCIENCES: A PATH TOWARD MODERN AND COMPETITIVE BIORESEARCH IN EASTERN SLOVAKIA (InterBioCass)

InterBioCass: Center of Excellence (CoE) guided by a coalition of excellent Partners

- University P.J. Safarik Kosice (UPJS), Slovakia (SK)**
 - Successful H2020 EU Training project
 - High potential for growth, and tech transfer
 - Skilled students and researchers from the East Europe
- Technical University Munich (TUM), Germany (DE)**
 - Partner with UPJS in Training H2020 project
 - Excellent research and project management
 - Experience with the creation of Centers of Excellence (CPA)
- Bio³ Biotech Cluster Development GmbH, DE**
 - Bio³ Cluster of 340 biotech/pharma companies
 - Coordinates the network of Bavarian biotech regions
 - Experienced, supported 200+ startups, 25 years
- University of Vienna, (UV), Austria (AT)**
 - Experience with International Training Network
 - Academia-industry know-how transfer and startup
 - Top experience with academic structures and management
- University of Oxford (UO), United Kingdom (UK)**
 - No. 1 university in Europe and in Top 10 world universities
 - Strong entrepreneurship, interdisciplinary departments
 - No. 1 in number of ERC grants (>407 as of 2021)

Project III: HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-01 (Teaming for Excellence) (15 mil. €)
EASTERN SLOVAKIA IN PATH TO INNOVATIVE GROWTH (ERA-CASSOVIA)

Bridging the excellence

- leading research hubs in Slovakia
- transforming our world into a better place
- perfect hub for cross-border collaboration
- place for experts and innovators where ideas start to fly

Project IV: SUPERCOMPUTER
70 mil. € - Recovery and resilience plan for Slovakia

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2.2 CasProt – current status

Erik Sedlák

Abstract: This presentation provides brief summary of the current status of the project CasProt and its influence on scientific outcomes of the shared laboratories of Center for Interdisciplinary Biosciences and Department of biophysics both in the number and quality of publications as well as in the the number of obtained grants.

CasProt – current status (selected slides)

2.3 The design of evolution and the evolution of design

Andreas Plückthun

Abstract: Combinatorial approaches in biology require appropriate screening methods for very large libraries. The library size, however, is almost always limited by the initial transformation steps following its assembly and ligation, as other all screening methods use cells or phages and viruses derived from them. Ribosome display is the first method for screening and selection of functional proteins performed completely in vitro and thus circumventing many drawbacks of in vivo systems. We review here the principle and applications of ribosome display for generating high-affinity antibodies from complex libraries. In ribosome display, the physical link between genotype and phenotype is accomplished by a mRNA-ribosome-protein complex that is used for selection.

Designed ankyrin repeat proteins (DARPin) can recognize targets with specificities and affinities that equal or surpass those of antibodies, but because of their robustness and extreme stability, they allow a multitude of more advanced formats and applications. I highlight recent advances in DARPin design, illustrates their properties, and gives some examples of their use. In research, they have been established as intracellular, real-time sensors of protein conformations and as crystallization chaperones. For future therapies, DARPins have been developed by advanced, structure-based protein engineering to selectively induce apoptosis in tumors by uncoupling surface receptors from their signaling cascades. They have also been used successfully for retargeting viruses. In ongoing clinical trials, DARPins have shown good safety and efficacy in macular degeneration diseases. These developments all ultimately exploit the high stability, solubility, and aggregation resistance of these molecules, permitting a wide range of conjugates and fusions to be produced and purified.

Comparison Fab fragment and DARPin

Modular binding mechanism

Conti *et al.*, Cell 1998: PDB ID 1BK6

The design of evolution and the evolution of design (selected slides)

Cell-specific gene delivery for therapy

a

Knob
Fiber shaft

b

Very stable trimer
Retargeting DARPin
C-terminus
Minimal linker

c

Extreme kinetic stability against dissociation
Forrer et al., *J. Mol. Biol.* **344**, 179 (2004)

Retargeting DARPin Knob-binding DARPin Trimerization motif
Flexible linker 1D3 SHP
Minimal linker

Dreier et al., *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **110**, E869 (2013)

DARPins are multifunctional molecules

Protein Purification

5-6 HOURS

Therapeutics

Diagnostics

Method Development

Functional Studies

Structural Biology

Cellular Imaging

Plückthun, A. (2015) *Annu. Rev. Pharmacol. Toxicol.* **55**, 489-511

2.4 Single molecule force spectroscopy for protein folding and cell adhesion

Matthias Rief

Abstract: Force spectroscopy has developed into an indispensable tool for studying folding and binding of proteins on a single molecule level in real time. The glucocorticoid receptor (GR) is an important transcription factor and drug target linked to a variety of biological functions and diseases. It is one of the most stringent physiological clients of the Hsp90/Hsp70/Hsp40 chaperone system. In this study, we used single-molecule force spectroscopy by optical tweezers to observe the interaction of the GR's ligand-binding domain (GR-LBD) with the Hsp70/Hsp40 chaperone system (Hsp70/40). We show in real time that sp70/40 can unfold the complete GR-LBD in a stepwise manner. Each unfolding step involves binding of an Hsp70 to the GR-LBD and subsequent adenosine triphosphate (ATP) hydrolysis, stimulated by Hsp40. The kinetics of chaperone-mediated unfolding depend on chaperone concentrations as well as the presence of the nucleotide exchange factor BAG1. We find that Hsp70/40 can stabilize new unfolding intermediates, showing that Hsp70/40 can directly interact with the folded core of the protein when working as an unfoldase. Our results support an unfolding mechanism where Hsp70 can directly bind to folded protein structures and unfold them upon ATP hydrolysis. These results provide important insights into the regulation of GR by Hsp70/40.

Single molecule force spectroscopy for protein folding and cell adhesion
(selected slides)

Optical Trap

Stigler, J., Ziegler, F., Gieseke, A., Gebhardt, J.C., and Rief, M., 2011. *Science*
 Rognoni L, Stigler J, Pelz B, Ylänne J, Rief M, 2012 *PNAS*
 Zoldak G, Stigler J, Pelz B, Li H, Rief M, 2013. *PNAS*
 Rognoni L, Most T, Zoldak G., Rief M, 2014. *PNAS*
 Ramm B., Stigler J, Hinczewski M, Thirumalai D, Herrmann H., Woehlke G., and Rief M, 2014. *PNAS*
 Bauer D., Merz D. R., Pelz B., Theisen K. E., Yacyshyn G., Mokranjac D., Dima R. I., Rief M., Zoldak G. 2015 *PNAS*
 Pelz B., Zoldak G., Zeller F., Zacharias M., Rief M. 2016 *Nat. Comm.*
 Kilchherr F, et al.. 2016 *Science*
 Grison, M., Merkel, U., Kostan, J., Djinovic-Carugo, K., and Rief, M. 2017 *PNAS*
 B Bauer, D., Meinhold, S., Jakob, R.P., Stigler, J., Merkel, U., Maier, T., Rief, M., and Zoldak, G. A 2018 *PNAS*
 Moessmer, P., Suren, T., Majdic, U., Dahiya, V., Rutz, D., Buchner, J., and Rief, M. 2022 *PNAS*

The Ligand Binding Domain of the Glucocorticoid Receptor

● Cysteine mutation ● Dexamethasone

- *In vitro* investigation of GR folding is severely hampered by aggregation
- Apo protein has a strong tendency for aggregation.
- Hormone is deeply buried inside the structure
- *In vivo*, hormone binding is strongly regulated by Chaperones (Hsp 70, 90, etc)

Suren et al., *PNAS*, 2018

Single molecule force spectroscopy for protein folding and cell adhesion
(selected slides)

Single molecule force spectroscopy for protein folding and cell adhesion
(selected slides)

2.5 Directed evolution of antibodies for detection of low abundant biomarkers in body fluids

Jozef Hanes

Abstract: Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative brain disorder in which progressive dementia occurs. The causes are still not clear. To date, there is no cure for AD and no FDA-approved biomarker. We developed a novel pT217 tau ELISA assay, which measures phosphorylated tau proteins on Thr217 in cerebrospinal fluid. We showed that this novel assay can distinguish AD from healthy individuals and AD from other neurodegenerative diseases with very high sensitivity and specificity and is more sensitive and specific compared to other currently used biomarkers. Because this assay was not sensitive enough to measure pT217 tau species in blood we improved the affinity of pT217-tau binding antibody by ribosome display. In collaboration with our partner, we developed a pT217 assay for blood and showed that it was possible to measure pT217 tau in all AD and control plasma samples.

Directed evolution of antibodies for detection of low abundant biomarkers in body fluids (selected slides)

Alzheimer's disease (AD)

- A neurodegenerative brain disorder in which progressive dementia occurs.
- The causes are still not clear
- To date, there is no cure for AD
- The prevalence of AD in 65-year-olds is 2%, in 70-year-olds 3%, 75-year-olds 6% and 85-year-olds 20%.
- Typical neuropathological findings in the brains of patients:
 - Neurofibrillary tangles, mainly contain pathological forms of tau proteins that are abnormally modified
 - Amyloid plaques consisting of aggregated amyloid peptides (AB40 and AB42)
 - AD Patients have abnormally elevated levels of total tau (tTau), phosphorylated tau (pT181-tau, pT217-tau) and NfL in CSF and blood, and abnormally decreased levels of AB42 in the CSF

Dr. A. Alzheimer

37th Meeting of psychiatrists of Southwest Germany Tübingen
3rd November 1906

Tangles

Plaques

6

Novel biomarkers for AD discovered: Tau phosphorylated on Thr-217

- is present in the extracellular space and CSF
- displays rapid turnover in physiological conditions
- correlates with amyloidosis

Tau Kinetics in Neurons and the Human Central Nervous System

Chihiro Sato,^{1,5,*} Nicolas R. Barthélemy,^{1,5} Kwasi G. Mawuenyega,¹ Bruce W. Patterson,² Brian A. Gordon,³ Jennifer Jockel-Balsarotti,¹ Melissa Sullivan,¹ Matthew J. Crisp,¹ Tom Kasten,¹ Kristopher M. Kirmess,² Nicholas M. Kanaan,⁴ Kevin E. Yarasheski,² Alaina Baker-Nigh,² Tammie L.S. Benzinger,³ Timothy M. Miller,^{1,5} Celeste M. Karch,^{5,6,*} and Randall J. Bateman^{1,5,7,8,*}

Neuron 2018

Tau hyperphosphorylation on T217 in cerebrospinal fluid is specifically associated to amyloid-β pathology

Nicolas R. Barthelemy, Randall J. Bateman, Philippe Marin, Francois Becher, Chihiro Sato, Sylvain Lehmann, Audrey Gabelle

[BioRxiv 2017](#)

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Directed evolution of antibodies for detection of low abundant biomarkers in body fluids (selected slides)

Novel pT217 tau ELISA assay

- We established pT217 ELISA assay using Axon Neuroscience R&D services antibodies: DC2E7 and DC2E2
- The sensitivity of the ELISA assay was not sufficient reliably measure pT217 tau species in CSF
- Solution:
 1. Use high sensitive technologies (digital ELISA)
 2. Improve affinities of antibodies
 3. Combination of 1. and 2.

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Directed evolution of antibodies for detection of low abundant biomarkers in body fluids (selected slides)

2.6 Transforming protein engineering: unleashing the power of kinetics, microfluidics and machine learning

Zbyněk Prokop^{1,2}

Martin Marek,¹ David Bednar,¹ Stanislav Mazurenko,^{1,2} Stavros Stavrakis,³ Andrew deMello,³ Jiri Damborsky^{1,2}

¹ Loschmidt Laboratories, Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

² International Centre for Clinical Research, St. Ann's Hospital, Brno, Czech Republic

³ Institute for Chemical and Bioengineering, ETH Zürich, Switzerland

Abstract: Proteins are fascinating molecules that have a wide range of applications in modern biotechnology. However, natural variants are often not fully equipped to handle the demanding conditions of biotechnological processes. The properties of proteins can effectively be modified using protein engineering. Recently, protein engineering has witnessed rapid growth in multidisciplinary, incorporating advanced methods such as modern kinetics, microfluidics, and artificial intelligence.[1] The modern kinetic analysis provides essential mechanism-based guidance for effective rational engineering. With the advancement of global analysis using numerical integration, the level of detail obtained from kinetic investigation depends mostly on the available data. The current trend of microfluidic lab-on-a-chip technology goes towards this direction. Microfluidic devices can perform thousands of analyses per second combinatorically, in reaction volumes ranging from nano- to femtoliters. Microfluidics thus significantly outperforms conventional analytical techniques in terms of throughput and sample requirements.[2,3] The synergy of high-throughput microfluidic analysis, modern numerical methods for global data analysis, and molecular

modelling provides a deep understanding of the specific protein property essential for its rational engineering. We also envision considerable potential for combining automated data collection via microfluidics with machine learning.[4]

References:

- [1] Vasina, M., Velecky, J., Planas-Iglesias, J., Marques, S. M., Skarupova, J., Damborsky, J., Bednar, D., Mazurenko, S., Prokop, Z., 2022: In-depth Analysis of Biocatalysts by Microfluidics: An Emerging Source of Data for Machine Learning. *Biotechnology Advances* **2023**, online, 108171
- [2] D. Hess, V. Dockalova, P. Kokkonen, D. Bednar, J. Damborsky, A. deMello, Z. Prokop, S. Stavrakis. Exploring Mechanism of Enzyme Catalysis by On-Chip Transient Kinetics Coupled with Global Data Analysis and Molecular Modelling, *Chem* **2021**, 7, 1066-1079.
- [3] Yang, T., Villos, A., Kunka, A., Grigolato, F., Arosio, P., Prokop, Z., deMello, A., Stavrakis, S. Droplet-Based Microfluidic Temperature-Jump Platform for the Rapid Assessment of Biomolecular Kinetics. *Analytical Chemistry* **2022**, 94: 16675–16684.
- [4] Mazurenko, S., Prokop, Z., Damborsky, J. Machine Learning in Enzyme Engineering. *ACS Catalysis* **2020**, 10: 1210-1223.

Transforming protein engineering: unleashing the power of kinetics, microfluidics and machine learning (selected slides)

Transforming protein engineering

the power of kinetics, microfluidics and machine learning

Zbyněk Prokop

Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic
ICRC, St. Ann's Faculty Hospital, Czech Republic

Symposium on directed evolution of proteins, Tatranská Lomnica, Slovak Republic, April 29th 2023

Modern biotechnology

Transforming protein engineering: unleashing the power of kinetics, microfluidics and machine learning (selected slides)

Tools for protein engineering

Bioinformatics 2018, 34: 3586-3588

Bioinformatics 35: 4986-4993 (2019)
Nucleic Acids Res. 47: W414-W422 (2019)

Nucleic Acids Res. 48, W356-W362 (2018)

Nucleic Acids Res. 45, W393-W399 (2017)

Nucleic Acids Res., 50 (W1): W465 (2022)

Bioinformatics 37, 23-28 (2021)

Protein engineering

RATIONAL DESIGN

1. Computer aided design

2. Site-directed mutagenesis

Individual mutated gene

3. Transformation

4. Protein expression

5. Protein purification

6. not applied

Constructed mutant enzyme

IMPROVED
ENZYME

7. Biochemical testing

DIRECTED EVOLUTION

1. Computer aided design

2. Random mutagenesis

Library of mutated genes
(>10,000 clones)

3. Transformation

4. Protein expression

5. not applied

6. Screening and selection

- stability
- selectivity
- affinity
- activity

Selected mutant enzymes

Transforming protein engineering: unleashing the power of kinetics, microfluidics and machine learning (selected slides)

Engineering Staphylokinase

ACS Catal. 2022, 12: 3807–3814

Comp. Struct. Biotech. J. 2022, 20: 1366–1377

Perspective of AI in protein engineering

DEEP MUTATIONAL SCANNING supervised learning

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS unsupervised learning

STRUCTURE PREDICTION deep learning

SEQUENCE BASED PREDICTION supervised learning (low No.)

STRUCTURE TO SEQUENCE deep learning

DOCKING deep learning

ACS Catal. 10 (2020) Nat. Comm. 9 (2018) Nature 596 (2021) Science 378 (2022) BioRxiv 2023 arXiv 2023

2.7 Directed self-assembly of spider silk protein on surfaces

Martin Humeník¹

A. Minařík², C. Heinritz¹, Z. Lamberger¹, K. Kocourková², H. Bargerl¹

¹ Department of Biomaterials, Faculty of Engineering Science, Universität Bayreuth, Prof.-Rüdiger-Bormann.Str. 1, 95447 Bayreuth, Germany, ² Department of Physics and Materials Engineering, Tomas Bata University in Zlín, Vavrečkova 275, 760 01 Zlín, Czech Republic

Abstract: We established DNA-spider silk conjugates using “click” coupling of the recombinant protein eADF4(C16) with short DNA strands to create hybrid materials. Whereas the spider silk moiety enabled self-assembly into nanofibrils controlled by phosphate ions in aqueous buffers, the DNA part enabled DNA specific fibril labeling (1) or sequence specific immobilization of DNA-spider silk conjugates (2). Recently, we developed surface nucleated self-assembly of the DNA-modified recombinant spider silk proteins into immobilized fibril-based networks, which revealed swelling and softening properties of nanohydrogels suitable as an enzyme depot (3). The DNA-functionalization in the highly hydrated, cell repellent networks could be used in a specific cell binding. For this, a mild lipid-DNA incorporation into cell membrane was employed, which showed high labelling efficiency as well as negligible cytotoxicity. Based on the complementarity of the nucleic acids, highly specific DNA-assisted immobilization of the cells on the spider silk nanohydrogels with tuneable cell densities was possible. Designed competitor DNA probes enabled the cell’s lift off on demand (4). We also employed modification of the nanohydrogels with DNA-aptamers capable of binding to cell markers to immobilize different types of cancer cells specifically (5). The principle of surface nucleated fibril self-assembly and nanohydrogel formation was further combined with photolithography. Using a positive-tone resist on an amino-reactive substrate, arbitrarily

shaped microwells were patterned, which bottom served to define the binding of spider silk nucleation sites and formation of the fibrillar networks (6). After stripping of the sacrificial photoresists, nanohydrogel micro-structured pattern were achieved enabling either the DNA-assisted immobilization of DNA-labelled cells (4) or the aptamer-cancer cell marker interactions with high spatial fidelity (5).

Figure 1. Micropatterning of cells on nanohydrogels. A) Optical profilometry of microwells after development of positive tone photoresist. B) AFM profile of the nanohydrogels assembled in the microwell after the photoresist stripping; C) DNA modified Jurkat cells immobilized on the complementary modified nanohydrogels; D) AFM profile of a boundary between the nanohydrogels with cells and a pegylated surface.

References

1. M. Humenik, T. Scheibel, Nanomaterial Building Blocks Based on Spider Silk–Oligonucleotide Conjugates. *ACS Nano* **8**, 1342–1349 (2014).
2. A. Molina, T. Scheibel, M. Humenik, Nanoscale patterning of surfaces via DNA directed spider silk assembly. *Biomacromolecules* **20**, 347–352 (2019).
3. M. Humenik, T. Preiß, S. Gödrich, G. Papastavrou, T. Scheibel, Functionalized DNA-spider silk nanohydrogels for controlled protein binding and release. *Mater. Today Bio* **6**, 100045 (2020).
4. C. Heinritz, Z. Lamberger, K. Kocourková, A. Minařík, M. Humenik, DNA functionalized spider silk nanohydrogels for specific cell attachment and patterning. *ACS Nano* **16**, 7626–7635 (2022).
5. Z. Lamberger, H. Bargel, M. Humenik, Aptamer-modified nanohydrogel microarrays for bioselective cancer cell immobilization. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **32**, 2207270 (2022).
6. Z. Lamberger, K. Kocourková, A. Minařík, M. Humenik, Dual patterning of self-assembling spider silk protein nanofibrillar networks. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **9**, 2201173 (2022).

Directed self-assembly of spider silk protein on surfaces (selected slides)

Directed self-assembly of spider silk protein on surfaces (selected slides)

Directed self-assembly of spider silk protein on surfaces (selected slides)

2.8 Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70

Gabriel Žoldák

Symposium on directed evolution of proteins
 Grand Hotel Praha, Tatranská Lomnica
 28th April - 1st May 2023

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 - DnaK

Assoc. prof. Gabriel Žoldák, DrSc.
 Center for interdisciplinary biosciences, Technology and Innovation Park
 University PJ Šafárik in Košice, Slovakia
 Cassovia New Industry Cluster, Košice, Slovakia

prof. Matthias Rief
 Technische Universität München, Center for Functional
 Protein Assemblies (CPA), Lehrstuhl für Biophysik E22,
 Garching b. München, Germany

Abstract: The lecture explored the relationship between structural mechanics and directed evolution of proteins, focusing on the benefits of structural mechanics for directed evolution and using the example of the allosteric Hsp70 molecular chaperone. Protein allostery, which involves functional regulation between distal sites within a protein, requires a communication channel. Recent 3D structures of Hsp70 have provided insights into the molecular pathways of allosteric signals, but direct mechanical probing of long-range allosteric coupling is lacking. Next, my lecture described a study using laser optical tweezers to examine the mechanical properties of a truncated two-domain DnaK(1-552ye) in apo/ADP/ATP- and peptide-bound states. The study finds that in the apo and ADP states, DnaK domains are mechanically stable and rigid, while in the ATP state, the substrate-binding domain is mechanically destabilized due to interdomain docking and the unfolding of the α -helical lid. The folding state of the SBD allows observation of the continuous ATP/ADP cycling of the enzyme in real-time with a single molecule, which is strictly coupled to the chemical steps of the ATP hydrolysis cycle even in the presence of peptide substrate.

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 (selected slides)

Structural mechanics of proteins and directed evolution

How to study protein structural mechanics

- Atomic force microscopy
- Optical tweezers
- Magnetic tweezers
- Acoustic spectroscopy

Zoldák G, Rief M. Force as a single molecule probe of multidimensional protein energy landscapes. *Curr Opin Struct Biol.* 2013 Feb;23(1):48-57.

Benefits of structural mechanics

Identification of key structural elements

Improved understanding of protein stability

Optimization of protein function

Development of new sensors/materials

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 - DnaK

Hsp70 chaperone undergoes large conformational changes during ATP cycle

Can we capture such subnanometer conformational changes by single-molecule force spectroscopy?

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 (selected slides)

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 - DnaK

Can we capture subnanometer conformational changes by single-molecule force spectroscopy?

Structure of adenylate kinase

Open-close fluctuations of Adk

Pelz B, Žoldák G, Zeller F, Zacharias M, Rief M. Subnanometre enzyme mechanics probed by single-molecule force spectroscopy. Nature Commun. 2016 Feb 24;7:10848.

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 - DnaK

- Mechanical destabilisation of the lid transforms Hsp70 into autoinhibited state
- For mechanical experiments: stabilising variant DnaK^{ye}

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 (selected slides)

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 - DnaK

- Monitoring of the coupling between ATP induced allosteric changes w/o peptide substrates

Structural mechanics of *E.coli* Hsp70 - DnaK

SUMMARY

- DnaKye has a highly rigid SBD which depends on nucleotide status of the NBD
- SBD opening and closing highly cooperative coupled to stability of the domains
- Peptide binding stabilizes β -subdomain while lid opening is uncoupled
- SBD docking and undocking occurs cooperatively

Singh A, Rief M, Žoldák G. Direct observation of chemo-mechanical coupling in DnaK by single-molecule force experiments. *Biophys J*. 2022 Dec 6;121(23):4729-4739

2.9 Directed evolution of staphylokinase by ribosome display

Mária Tomková¹

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Abstract: Ischemic stroke and myocardial infarct are leading causes of death and disability world-wide. Usage of currently available thrombolytics is limited due to their high immunogenicity and haemorrhagic complications. Staphylokinase (SAK) is a single chain extracellular protein secreted by *Staphylococcus aureus*. It initiates the fibrinolytic cascade to help invading bacterium move deeper into the tissues. SAK is highly fibrin specific, and its characteristics makes it a promising new thrombolytic target. However, not all SAK features are optimized for its practical applications, leaving a room for its improvement. Engineering the affinity and selectivity of SAK could increase its residence time on plasmin, thus reducing the severity of side effects.

Directed evolution is a powerful approach to tailor protein properties toward new or enhanced functions. We employed ribosome display, in vitro selection, and evolution method, to improve SAK affinity for plasmin. Human plasmin was used as an antigen, against which SAK variants were selected.

We have successfully implemented selection of SAK variants by ribosome display and after first round of display we proved that it is feasible to evolve SAK by this technology. Evolution techniques usually require several consecutive rounds; therefore, we accomplished six rounds of the display. Sequencing of individual clones after every round of ribosome display revealed some identical amino acid substitutions (hot spots), that were found in several different mutants, indicating that such residues might be involved in SAK-plasmin interaction and its replacement might change SAK property towards higher plasmin affinity. We expressed and purified wild type SAK and several mutant SAK proteins and we determined their in vitro activity and stability.

Inefficient binding to plasmin is the main factor limiting overall SAK effectivity. Enhancement of SAK's affinity for plasmin is a highly desirable objective. Preliminary data obtained from SAK engineered by ribosome display showed that the evolution approach has high potential to improve the properties of SAK. However, to prove this statement we need to perform detailed biophysical characterisation of selected mutants.

Directed evolution of staphylokinase by ribosome display (selected slides)

Thrombosis-thrombolysis-thrombolytics

Coagulation cascade

Prothrombin → Thrombin → Fibrinogen → Fibrin net → Blood clot

Fibrinolytic cascade

Plasminogen → Plasmin → Fibrin degradation

Limitations of traditionally applied thrombolytics

- Internal bleeding
- Rapid clearance from circulation – secondary blood clots
- Allergic reaction
- Expensive production

Mican et al. Structural Biology and Protein Engineering of Thrombolytics. Comput Struct Biotechnol J. 2019

Staphylokinase (SAK)

PDB identifikátor: 1BUI

- Extracellular bacterial protein
- 15.5 kDa, no glycosylation, no disulfide bridges
- Virulence factors** facilitating bacterial penetration into the surrounding tissues = thrombolytic properties
- Distinct from the physiological plasminogen activators
- Non-direct plasminogen activator** – does not have enzymatic activity, forms 1:1 complex with plasmin
- SAK-Plm complex provides an exosite onto which the substrate can dock in an optimal orientation = cofactor
- Non-immunogenic SAK Frida variant** - lacks immunogenic properties due replacement of three amino acids (Lys74Ala, Glu75Ala, and Arg77Ala) in the immunogenic epitope of the SAK molecule
- Commercially available in Russia as Fortelysin
- Non-inferior to alteplase for patients with acute ischaemic stroke (Gusev et al., 2021)

SAK
uPlm product uPlm partner

Why do we want to engineer SAK?

SAK Advantages

- Highly **fibrin selective** in human plasma – does not cause systematic plasminogen activation, no bleeding complications
- Low production costs

SAK Disadvantages

- Immunogenic
- Short plasma life (6.5 minutes)
- Low plasmin affinity

Efforts to improve SAK properties

Our approach – Improvement of binding strength between SAK and plasmin by ribosome display

Strategy for testing of selected SAK variants

In vitro acellular protein expression/ no purification

- First screening of SAK variants
- **Activity assay**

Small volume expression/ low level SAK purification

- His-Tag protein purification
- Testing of SAK variants expressibility
- **Activity assay**

Large volume expression/ high level SAK purification

- His-Tag protein purification
- **Size exclusion chromatography** purification (SEC)
- **Protein thermal stability** – differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and circular dichroism (CD)
- **SAK-Plm interaction testing** by surface plasmon resonance (SPR)

Directed evolution of staphylokinase by ribosome display (selected slides)

Concluding remarks and perspectives

- We tailored ribosome display technique for selection of staphylokinase variants with higher affinity
- We set up the strategy for screening and characterization of SAK variants selected by ribosome display (activity, thermal stability, affinity)
- We tested several selected SAK variants for activity, SAK WT and Frida for thermal stability
- Variant 10.4 maintain similar activity as WT
- We want to select SAK Frida variants in further rounds of ribosome display
- Biophysical characterization of selected SAK variants

2.10 Design of genetically encoded photosensitizers

Erik Sedlák and Kristína Felčíková

Abstract: Flavin mononucleotide (FMN) belongs to the group of very efficient endogenous photosensitizers producing singlet oxygen, $^1\text{O}_2$, but with limited ability to be targeted. On the other hand, in genetically encoded photosensitizers, which can be targeted by means of various tags, the efficiency of FMN to produce $^1\text{O}_2$ is significantly diminished due to its interactions with surrounding amino acid residues. Recently, an increase of $^1\text{O}_2$ production yield by FMN buried in a protein matrix was achieved by a decrease of quenching of the cofactor excited states by weakening of the protein-FMN interactions while still forming a complex. Here, we suggest an alternative approach which relies on the blue light irradiation-induced dissociation of FMN to solvent. This dissociation unlocks the full capacity of FMN as $^1\text{O}_2$ producer. Our suggestion is based on the study of an irradiation effect on two variants of the LOV2 domain from *Avena sativa*; wild type, AsLOV2 wt, and the variant with a replaced cysteine residue, AsLOV2 C450A. We detected irradiation-induced conformational changes as well as oxidation of several amino acids in both AsLOV2 variants. Detailed analysis of these observations indicates that irradiation-induced increase in $^1\text{O}_2$ production is caused by a release of FMN from the protein. Moreover, an increased FMN dissociation from AsLOV2 wt in comparison with AsLOV2 C450A points to a role of C450 oxidation in repelling the cofactor from the protein. These observations led us to a hypothesis that introducing of $^1\text{O}_2$ oxidation prone aminoacids, such as cysteine, methionine into binding site of isoalloxazine ring of flavoprotein may lead to more efficient genetically encoded photosensitizers.

Design of genetically encoded photosensitizers (selected slides)

Design of genetically encoded photosensitizers (selected slides)

Genetically-encoded photosensitizers

KillerRed
 Type I
 $O_2 \xrightarrow{h\nu, KR} O_2^{\bullet-}$

miniSOG
 Type II
 $O_2 \xrightarrow{h\nu, SOG} {}^1O_2$

Westberg et al. (2019) *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 57, 56-62.

Westberg et al. (2015) *JACS* 137, 1632-1642.

Irradiation effect on singlet oxygen production of LOV2

A C450A
 1O_2 phosphorescence [counts] vs Time [$\times 10^{-6}$ s]

B wt
 1O_2 phosphorescence [counts] vs Time [$\times 10^{-6}$ s]

The time-course of the singlet oxygen phosphorescence signal for AsLOV2 C450A (A) and AsLOV2 *wt* (B) at different irradiation levels. The six curves were fitted in a global fitting procedure; the lines represent the fitted results. Insets: The decay of the FMN triplet state absorbance at 633 nm following the excitation laser pulse as measured for AsLOV2 C450A and AsLOV2 *wt*.

Petrenčáková et al. (2020) *Sci. Rep.* 10, 4119.

Design of genetically encoded photosensitizers (selected slides)

3. EARLY RESEARCHER'S PRESENTATIONS

3.1 Directed evolution of enzymes – the case of HLDs

Veronika Dzurillová

Abstract: Haloalkane dehalogenases represent a group of hydrolases, which are involved in biodegradation of prominent toxic environmental pollutant such as 1,2,3-trichloropropane. These enzymes catalyze the cleavage of carbon-halogen bond, by which toxic compound lost their toxicity, resistance to degradation and facilitate their conversion to less toxic alcohols. HLDs have also high application potential in the field of bioremediation, biocatalysis or biomonitoring of environmental pollutants. However, their widespread utilisation still has many limitations such as insufficient stability and catalytic activity. We aimed to enhance these properties by directed evolution approach and ribosome display method using the principle of HaloTag technology. We showed feasibility using ribosome display in combination with HaloTag technology in evolution directed engineering of enhanced haloalkane dehalogenases. After several rounds of ribosome display with randomized DhaA library were reached enrichment towards specific binders. Sequence analysis showed that individual selected mutants contain different point mutations, as well as small fraction contain extensive deletion. Identified deletion is situated within enzyme tunnel, important part of enzyme that has been previously targeted by rational design and directed evolution. By binding assay were identified several enhanced binders. Mutants from binding assay were showed to be 2-4 times better compare to wt DhaA, but following overexpression of proteins and biophysical characterization of mutant D15 lead to conclusion that proteins are denaturated/insoluble – forms inclusion bodies. Our results leads to conclusion, that inability to obtain enhanced mutants from enriched library has root in usement starting enzyme for engineering with insufficient stability - DhaA with mutated phenylalanine.

Directed evolution of enzymes – the case of HLDs (selected slides)

Haloalkane dehalogenases (HLDs)

- alpha/beta hydrolases (mostly bacterial origin) with wide substrate specificity
- catalyse hydrolytic cleavage of carbon-halogen bonds in various halogenated organic compounds

cap domain

N-term

alpha/beta hydrolase fold domain

C-term

zoom to active site

Asn41

Trp107

His272

Asp106

Glu150

Examples of HLDs substrates.

Tertiary structure of HLD DhaA and topology of catalytic pentad inside the active site of DhaA [PDB: 4HZG]

2

Haloalkane dehalogenases (HLDs)

HLDs are valuable biocatalysts with immense application potential.

R-X haloalkane

HLD

R-OH alcohol

regenerated coenzyme

Biocatalysis

Bioremediation

Cell imaging & protein analysis

Biosensing

Decontamination

However, widespread utilisation of HLDs is still limited by their properties – insufficient stability and catalytic activity.

Koudelakova, T., Bidmanova, S., Dvorak, P., Pavelka, A., Chaloupkova, R., Prokop, Z., & Damborsky, J. (2013). Haloalkane dehalogenases: biotechnological applications. *Biotechnology journal*, 8(1), 32–45.

3

Directed evolution of enzymes – the case of HLDs (selected slides)

Ribosome display

- enzyme DhaA
- error-prone PCR

• selection of mutants in 3-5 consecutive selection rounds

HaloTag Technology
 His → Phe

Los, Georgyi V et al. (2008). HaloTag: a novel protein labeling technology for cell imaging and protein analysis. ACS chemical biology vol. 3,6 : 373-82.

6

Ribosome display with DhaA library

- home-made S30 extract

- commercial in vitro expression system

L- 100 bp DNA ladder, 1,3,5 – negative controls, 1-2 – sample from the well without the substrate, 3-4 – reverse transcribed mRNA after *in vitro* transcription, 5-6 –sample from the well with the substrate
 Reverse transcription without reverse transcriptase [-] Reverse transcription with reverse transcriptase [+]

B. Test of influence of different concentration of GdnHCl and urea

Ribosome display with DhaA-HaloTag library including different concentration of guanidine hydrochlorid and urea within washing step. L – 100 bp DNA ladder. 1-14 samples from the well without target, 15-16 mRNA reverse transcribed after *in vitro* transcription. 1,3,5,7,9,11,13,15- negative controls.

8

Directed evolution of enzymes – the case of HLDs (selected slides)

Sequence analysis of DhaA library

A.

position 102 124 132-144

B.

loop L9 cap domain active site of DhaA

Leu 102 Lys124 α/β -hydrolase

Asn41 Trp107 Asp106 His272 Glu130

L 1 2 3 4 5

150 kDa
100 kDa
75 kDa
50 kDa
37 kDa
25 kDa
20 kDa
15 kDa

SDS-PAGE profile of purification of DhaA mutant with deletion by affinity chromatography expressed at 37°C in *E. coli* BL21(DE3). The desired protein was present at 33 kDa. L – supernatant of lysed cells 2 – pellet of lysed cells 3 – flowthrough 4 – washing of the column 5 – elution fraction with 500 mM imidazol

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The Role of Spontaneous Cap Domain Mutations in Haloalkane Dehalogenase Specificity and Evolution*

(Received for publication, February 23, 1994, and in revised form, April 22, 1994)

Frens Pries, Arjan J. van den Wijngaard, Rolf Bos, Marjan Pentenga, and Dick B. Janssen
From the Department of Biochemistry, Groningen Biomolecular Sciences and Biotechnology, University of Groningen, Nijenborgh 4, 9747 AG Groningen, The Netherlands

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Binding assay

- Inactive mutants – test for binding (covalent attachment) of fluorescent label

100 nM TMR

Relative fluorescence (a.u.)

Relative binding of TMR

Test of binding of TMR ligand by DhaAHT, DhaA protein and mutants selected by ribosome display. Individual columns represents relative amount of non-bound probe after 5 min incubation with 100 nM TMR probe.

→ Improved mutants: D4, D6, D7, D9, D14, **D15**, D16, D17, D18

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3.2 Aggregation mechanism of myelomatic human light chain

Veronika Džupponová

Abstract: Protein stability is a crucial property for the proper biological function of proteins. Low protein stability leads to unfolding, followed by the formation of aggregates that are pathological to the body and, in many cases, cause serious diseases. Such diseases include amyloidosis and multiple myeloma of the immunoglobulin light chain. Multiple myeloma (MM) is a haematological malignancy characterized by clonal proliferation of plasma cells that stop produce full-length antibodies, and they produce the monoclonal parts of the antibody - the light chain in huge excess. It passes into the bloodstream and creates extracellular sediments in vital organs. Understanding the molecular nature of protein aggregation and the effect of the physicochemical environment that accelerates the conversion of functional forms of proteins into pathogenic aggregates is a key to discovering effective strategies to decline the high morbidity of these leukemic diseases. At the same time, discovering limiting steps in the aggregation would enable the rational development of drugs inhibiting the formation of toxic aggregates. Here, we examined the aggregation mechanism and structures of the pathological human multiple myeloma light chain aggregates (hLC) after disrupting stabilizing disulfide bonds by various reducing agents. The aggregation kinetics were measured in the presence of three commonly used disulfide reducers (TCEP, DTT and glutathione), and the resulting aggregates were visualized by the combination of light and confocal/super-resolution STED microscopy. We find that aggregation kinetics can be described by two apparent macroscopic rate constants of the Finke-Watzky model related to the nucleation and the growth process. Surprisingly, the growth rate constants decreased at higher protein concentrations, which we interpret as the involvement of an aggregation active monomer particle that is successively depleted at high concentrations due to shifts in a monomer/dimer equilibrium. Three-dimensional visualization of the overall structures of the final aggregates at submicrometer resolution showed variable, reducer-specific branched morphologies with non-trivial fractal dimensions. Thus, the disruption of the stabilizing disulfide bonds in hLC leads to specific large, branched aggregates formed by the monomer-addition mechanism.

Aggregation mechanism of myelomatic human light chain (selected slides)

Amyloidosis of light chain

Healthy bone marrow → Plasma cell → Antibodies

Neoplastic transformation → Multiple myeloma → Myeloma cell → Excess of free light chains

Excess of free light chains → Unstable → Amyloid fibrils → Organ damage (Liver, Kidney, Heart)

28. 5. 2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

CasProt

JTO LC – role of disulfide bonds

Monomer A
Monomer B
Cysteine

SDS-PAGE

	reduction	nonreduction
46.8 kD		dimer
23.4 kD	monomer	monomer

28. 5. 2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

CasProt

Aggregation mechanism of myelomatic human light chain (selected slides)

JTO LC – role of disulfide bonds

Džupponová V., Žoldák G. (2023). Aggregation mechanism and branched 3D morphologies of pathological human light chain proteins under reducing conditions. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces*. 221, 112983.

28. 5. 2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

[JTO] concentration dependence

Analysis – extended Finke Watzky model

28. 5. 2023

Funded by EU, Horizon 2020 project N° 952333

3.3 Computational evolutionary analysis of insertion and deletion events in bacterial Hsp70

Michal Gala

Abstract: Heat shock proteins 70 (Hsp70) are molecular chaperones that comprise a nucleotide-binding domain (NBD) and a substrate-binding domain (SBD), the latter of which is responsible for binding protein clients. Upon ATP binding to the NBD, the interface between the α/β subdomains of the SBD undergoes conformational changes, resulting in its opening and subsequent docking onto the NBD. The stabilization of allosteric effects is facilitated by the interdomain contacts between the NBD and SBD that have recently been established. Here, we investigate the impact of Hsp70 evolution on the formation of subdomain interfaces and their subsequent opening. Insertion and deletion events, commonly referred to as indels, can significantly impact mechanical events. This is due to the fact that such changes introduce a collective shift in the pairing interactions at communicating interfaces. Through an analysis of multiple sequence alignment data obtained from the Swiss-Prot/UniProt database, a number of indel-free regions (IFR) have been identified within Hsp70. The two most sizable IFRs are situated in interdomain regions that engage in allosteric conformational changes. We speculate that the reduced probability of indel occurrence in these regions can be attributed to the disruptive effects of indel events on the mechanical balance of the protein, leading to functional impairment. The rational design of functional allosteric machines necessitates the incorporation of a notion of balance among structural components.

Computational evolutionary analysis of insertion and deletion events in bacterial Hsp70 (selected slides)

Computational evolutionary analysis of insertion and deletion events in bacterial Hsp70 (selected slides)

Computational evolutionary analysis of insertion and deletion events in bacterial Hsp70 (selected slides)

3.4 Self-assembly of recombinant spider silk protein

Veronika Hovanová

Symposium on directed evolution of proteins
Grand Hotel Praha, Tatranské Lomnicka
April 28th, 2023- May 1st, 2023

Self-assembly of recombinant spider silk protein

Veronika Hovanová

CIB-TIP UPJŠ
Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice

Abstract: Protein nanofibrils are a new type of nanofibrils that have great potential as scaffolds for various materials and nanocomposites. The eADF4(C16) protein, a recombinant spider silk protein based on the dragline protein *Araneus diandematus* fibroin 4 (ADF4), forms amyloid-like nanofibrils when exposed to potassium phosphate. However, the molecular mechanism underlying the protein's fibrillization process is not fully understood yet. A detailed kinetic study of fibrillization was investigated in dependence on protein concentration and temperature. The online platform AmyloFit was used to globally fit the kinetic data obtained during nucleated self-assembly. The results showed that the fibrils are formed through the mechanisms of secondary nucleation.

Self-assembly of recombinant spider silk protein (selected slides)

Spider silk

Natural Spider Silk

Dragline silk
Araneus diadematus

repetitive core
 $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{NR}-\text{SH}$ | 10-50 amino acids | 20-100 repeats | $\text{NR}-\text{COOH}-\text{SH}$

Recombinant Spider Silk

design of typical repetitive motifs (consensus motifs) based on sequences from natural spider silk proteins, optimized for bacterial production

eADF4(C16)
module C
 $\text{GSSAAAAAAAASGPGGYGPENQGPSGPGGYGPGGP}$

$\text{H}_2\text{N}-$ [16 repeats] $-\text{COOH}$

Huemmerich et al. *Biochemistry*, 2004, 43, 13604-13612.
Heidebrecht et al., *Adv. Appl. Microbiol.* 2013, 82.

2 | 30/04/2023

Processing of eADF4(C16)

module C
 $\text{GSSAAAAAAAASGPGGYGPENQGPSGPGGYGPGGP}$

$\text{H}_2\text{N}-$ [16 repeats] $-\text{COOH}$

Humenik, M. et al. 2011, *Polymers*, 1, 640-661.

3 | 30/04/2023

Self-assembly of recombinant spider silk protein (selected slides)

//

Scientific questions

- 1.) What molecular events are present by nanofibrils formation?
- 2.) Can a kinetic model of fibrillization be determined ?
- 3.) How will different conditions change the properties of the nanofibrils and, consequently, the formed higher structures?

Kliknite sem a zadajte text

4 | 30/04/2023

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Protein self-assembly into nanofibrils

aqueous
eADF4(C16)
solution

> 250
mM KPi

< 250
mM KPi

phase-
separation

nucleation and
elongation

Humenik M., Magdeburg M., Scheibel T. (2014) Influence of repeat numbers on self-assembly rates of repetitive recombinant spider silk proteins. *J Struct Biol* 186:431-437.

Kliknite sem a zadajte text

6 | 30/04/2023

Self-assembly of recombinant spider silk protein (selected slides)

